

Bibliometric Analysis of Post-Graduation Dissertation of Library and Information Science submitted at Bangalore North University During Period From 2020-2023

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Abstract:

The present research study focussed on Bibliometric Analysis of Post-Graduation Dissertation of Library and Information Science submitted at Bangalore North University During Period From 2020-2023. A total of 1409 citations were identified from 45 PG dissertations. The highest 15(33.33%) number of dissertations were submitted in 2021 followed by the highest 782(55.50%) were from "Journal articles", 305(39.01%) were "Single Author", 34(4.35%) are from the journal of "Library Progress" published from "India", 496(63.43%) were from the period "2013-2023".

1 Introduction

Bibliometric studies, which are based on different information aspects including author, title, subject, and citations, have been carried out on publications primarily associated with scientific fields. This kind of analysis offers helpful markers of trends, scientific output, research focus across disciplines, and publication preferences of researchers.¹

A quantitative and qualitative research technique called bibliometric analysis examines publications and their citations to identify trends in the creation and sharing of knowledge. It is a useful instrument for assessing the significance of studies and spotting new patterns in a certain area. By looking at the nations, organisations, and authors

¹Thavamani, K.(2013). "Directory of Open Access Journals: A Bibliometric Study of Library and Information Science. "Collaborative Librarianship, 5(4), 246-254.

conducting research, bibliometric analysis can reveal details about the makeup of a certain field's research.²

A research methodology called bibliometrics analyses and assesses the dynamics, structure, and significance of scientific research using quantitative techniques.³

The field was created by Derek de Solla Price and Visalia Vasilevich Nazimova with the intention of giving historians and sociologists of science research instruments.⁴

1.2 Meaning and Definitions

Bibliometric is a study or measurement of format aspects of texts, documents, books and information. The term Bibliometric was first used by **Pritchard in 1969**, as the application of mathematical and statistical methods to books and other media of communication. It included relationship among number of papers growth of literature and patterns of library database usage. Bibliographic databases are representative samples of publication activity in the field of knowledge. Bibliometric methods are most often used in the field of library and information science many research fields use bibliometric methods to explore the impact of their field. Bibliometric has changed out all recognition since 1958.⁵

The term bibliometric was first used by **Paul Otlet in 1934**, and defined as "the measurement of all aspects related to the publication and reading of books and documents."⁶ **Singh, V. P. & Kauri, J:** "A quantitative method of evaluating and analysing the publication patterns, citation frequencies, and impact of scientific literature, using statistical and mathematical techniques to identify trends, patterns, and correlations in the data."⁷

²Kim, J. (2023). Bibliometric Analysis of Research Articles on Virtual Reality in the Field of Pain Medicine Published from 1993 to 202. *Journal of Pain Research*, 16, 3881—3893.

³Moed, H. (2008). "The History of Bibliometrics". *Scientometrics*, 751, 3-15.

⁴Krishnappa, M, Mariraj Sedam, and Puttesha,C. (2022). Bibliometrics: An overview. *International Advanced Research Journal in Science, Engineering and Technology*, 9(2).

⁵Chellappandi,P.&Vijayakumar,C,S.(2018).Bibliometrics,Scientometrics,Webometrics/Cybermetrics,Infor metrics and Altmetrics - An Emerging Field in Library and Information Science Research. *International Journal of Education*, 7(1), . 5–8.

⁶Rousseau, Ronald (2014). "Library Science: Forgotten Founder of Bibliometric". *Nature*. **510** (7504): 218. Bibcode: 2014Natur. 510..218R.

⁷ Singh, V. P., & Kauri, J. (2022). Bibliometric and Scientometrics: An Overview. In *Research Methods and Methodologies in Social Sciences* (pp. 231-244). Springer.

1.4 Library and information Science

2011 will mark the 100th anniversary of library and information science (LIS) education in India. It is necessary to reflect on the current state of LIS and identify areas that require development. The growth and development are depicted in history, which gives such a research perspective. India started offering LIS courses from the turn of the 20th century. Sayyaji Rao Gaekwad, the former Maharaja of the former princely State of Baroda, is often credited in literature with starting the LIS education movement in the nation. The first librarians to teach LIS in India were American librarians William Alanson Borden and Asa Don Dickinson. Training librarians in our nation is also credited to John MacFarlane, an Englishman who was the first librarian of the Imperial Library (now the National Library, Kolkata). Actually, the first instance of LIS education in India that has been documented in the literature is MacFarlane's training program. Training programs for the Imperial Library's employees were organised between 1901 and 1906. Later, it was expanded to include librarians employed in other states in addition to Calcutta.⁸

Library and information science (LIS) are two interconnected disciplines that deal with the organization, access, collection, and regulation of information, both in physical and digital forms. These are two original disciplines, library science and information science, but they are within the same field of study. Library science is applied information science. Library science is both an application and a subfield of information science.⁹

2. Literature Review

- **Reyes, Farooq.** (2024). Conducted research on A review of knowledge Information management research in the past three decades the number of publications has significantly increased in the past decade, 88.4% of authors contribute at least a single article, 8.3% of authors published two articles, 2% of the

⁸Krishan Kumar and Jaideep Sharma. (2010). Library and Information Science Education in India: A Historical Perspective. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*,30(5), 3-8.

⁹ Coleman, A. (2002). Interdisciplinary: The Road Ahead for Education in Digital Libraries.D- Lib Magazine, 8:8/9.

authors published three documents and 0.6% of the authors contribute four papers.¹⁰

- **Ramos, Corderio, Emerson.(2024).**Examine the Knowledge management in small and medium enterprises: a systematic literature review, bibliometric analysis, and research agenda This study contributes to both practitioners and academics by providing a list of 19 barriers, 12 factors and 36 research questions related to knowledge management in small and medium-sized companies to develop future theoretical and practical studies.¹¹
- **Li, Ming.-yueh,Theresa.(2024).** Carried out a study on Bibliometric analysis of the journal literature on women’s studies. literature over the period from 1900 to 2013. Using computer analysis for bibliometric techniques, most of the document types in the area of women’s studies are in the form of research articles, review articles and book reviews. The United States of America and the United Kingdom contribute the largest number of articles. 117 core journals containing 33% of the women’s studies journal articles have been identified through the application of Bradford’s law on journal distribution.¹²
- **Damoon Razmjooei.(2024).** Has conducted a study on A bibliometric analysis of the literature on circular economy and sustainability in maritime studies. From 1970 to 2010, a few papers were published on this topic, while after 2010 the number of publications exhibited a considerable increasing trend. More specifically, the TP in 2021 (139) was about twenty times as great as that in 2001 (7). In order to investigate the future research on circularity in the SM field, a fitting curve and a formula for the trend changes in publications were constructed.¹³

¹⁰Farooq, R. (2024) A review of knowledge Information management research in the past three decades. *VINE Journal of and Knowledge Management Systems*, 339-378.

¹⁸Ramos Corderio, Emerson. (2024). Knowledge management in small and medium enterprises: a systematic literature review, bibliometric analysis, and research agenda. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 28(2), 590-612.

¹²Li, Minh-yueh Theresa., (2024). Bibliometric analysis of the journal literature on women’s studies. Springer link, 113, 705–734.

¹³Damoon Razmjooei, M. A.-A. (2024). A bibliometric analysis of the literature on circular economy and sustainability in maritime studies. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 26, 5509–5536,

- **Shafeeque and Hanaa (2024).** Examine A holistic approach to augmented reality-related research in tourism: through bibliometric analysis shows a recent rise in research on AR in the tourism industry. The top 10 studies in the topic had a combined total of 1749 citations, while the authors found three papers with more than 200 Scopus citations.¹⁴
- **Farhat, Faiza. (2024).** Carried out a research on The scholarly footprint of ChatGPT: a bibliometric analysis of the early outbreak phase during the period of 2022–2023. A total of 533 documents were produced from 341 sources from 87 different countries involving 1,434 authors, indicating a thriving research interest The total corpus involved 1,434 authors, with 159 of them contributing to single-authored documents. This represents a significant collaboration rate of 88.91%, highlighting the collaborative network within the research area.¹⁵
- **Oludapo, Samson, & Noel Carroll, Markus Helfert.(2024)** Examine study on Why do so many digital transformations fail? A bibliometric analysis and future research agenda. From the WoS search, we obtained 740 papers. Out of these, 702 were published in English, and eight were editorials. We specifically focused on research fields related to Information Systems (IS), excluding conference materials and reviews lacking any significance to DT, resulting in a selection of 120 valid papers for our analysis Among these 120 studies, 14.1 % (17) were single-authored. In addition, the authors used a substantial pool of keywords, totalling 521 keywords.¹⁶

3. Statement of the problem

The present Research problem is entitled as “Bibliometric Analysis of Post-Graduation Dissertation of Library and Information Science submitted at Bangalore North University During Period From 2020-2023”.

¹⁴ Shafeeque M. Hanaa, A. P. (2024). A holistic approach to augmented reality-related research in tourism: through bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, 7(1).

¹⁵ Farhat, Faiza. (2024). The scholarly footprint of ChatGPT: a bibliometric analysis of the early outbreak phase. *SYSTEMATIC REVIEW* article, 6.

¹⁶Oludapo, Samson, & Noel Carroll, Markus Helfert.(2024). Why do so many digital transformations fail? A bibliometric analysis and future research agenda. *Journal of Business Research*, 174.

4. Need for the study

It makes use of bibliographic citations, which are essential act of the primary scientific communication. The technique of citation analysis involves the process of collection, counting, analysis and interpretation of citations, given various types of literature and thereby help in identification of signification sources of information individuals, institutions and other aggregated of scientific activity.

5 Objectives of the study

- To know year wise submission of PG Dissertations in Library and information science by BNU
- To find out Types of documents cited by researchers.
- To verify the Authorship pattern of Citations
- To find out Ranking of periodicals
- To know Geographical wise distribution of journals
- To Find out Age wise distribution of journal citations.

6. Scope and Limitations of the Study

The present study limited to “Bibliometric Analysis of Post-Graduation Dissertation of Library and Information Science by BNU During Period From 2020-2023”.

7. Sources Used for data collection

For present research study researcher used as a tool for Post-Graduation Dissertation of Library and Information Science by BNU During Period From 2020-2023”.

8. Methodology

The data has been collected from Post-Graduation Dissertation of Library and Information Science by BNU During Period From 2020-2023”. The citation technique was adopted for the present study. The collected data is entered in MS Excel sheet According to AACR2 cataloguing code. And also tabulated, presented and interpreted with the help of tables and graphs. and also search journal country names in SCIMOG Website.

9. Hypotheses

H1 There is a significant relationship between year wise submission of PG Dissertations towards Types of documents cited by researchers.

H2 There is a Significant relationship between Ranking of periodicals towards Geographical wise distribution of journals

H3 There is a Significant relationship between Types of documents cited by researchers. Towards Age wise distribution of journal citations.

10. Data Analysis and interpretation

Table 1. year wise submission of PG Dissertations in LISc

Sl. No	Year	Citations	No. of dissertations submitted	%
1	2020	443	09	20
2	2021	402	15	33.33
3	2022	311	10	22.22
4	2023	253	11	24.45
Total		1409	45	100

It is observed in table 1 that year wise submission of PG Dissertations in LISc. A total of 1409 citations were identified from 45 PG dissertations. The highest 15(33.33%) number of dissertations were submitted in 2021. Followed by 11(24.45%) were Submitted in 2023, 10(22.22%) were submitted in 2022 and 9(20%) were submitted in the year 2020.

Fig 1. Year wise submission of PG Dissertations in LISc.

Table : 2 Types of documents cited by Researchers

SL. NO	Rank no	Types of documents	Citations	%	Cumulative of citations	%
1	1	Journal articles	782	55.50	782	55.50
2	2	Electronic Sources	217	15.40	999	70.90
3	3	Conference Proceedings	148	10.50	1,147	81.40
4	4	Books	133	9.44	1,280	90.84
5	5	Incomplete References	89	6.31	1,369	97.16
6	6	News papers	16	1.14	1,385	98.29
7	7	Thesis and Dissertations	14	0.99	1,399	99.29
8	8	Annual Reports	4	0.29	1,403	99.57
9	9	Hank Books	3	0.21	1,406	99.78
10	10	Magazines	2	0.15	1,408	99.92
11	11	Illustrated Book	1	0.07	1,409	100
Total			1409	100		

It is observed in table 2 that types of documents cited by researchers. A total of 1409 citations were identified out of which the highest 782(55.50%) were from “Journal articles” followed by 217(15.40%) were from “Electronic sources”, 148(10.50%) were from “Conference proceedings”, 133(9.44%) were from “Books” 89(6.31%) were from “Incomplete References”, 16(1.14%) were from “Newspapers”, 14(0.99%) were from “Thesis and Dissertations” 4(0.29%) were from “Annual Reports”, 3(0.21%) were from “Hand Books”, 2(0.15%) were from “Magazines” and 1(0.07%) were from “Illustrated Books”.

Fig.2 Types of documents cited by researchers.

Table: 3 Authorship patterns of Citations

Sl. no	No. of. Authors	No. of Citations	%
1	Single Author	305	39.01
2	Above Two authors	477	60.99
	Total	782	100

It is observed in T 3 that Authorship pattern of Citations. A total of 782 citations there are 305(39.01%) were “Single Author” followed by 477(60.99%) were from Above Two authors.

Fig .3 Authorship patterns of Citations.**Table 4 Ranking of periodicals**

SL. NO	Rank no	Journal Names	No. of Citations	%	Cumulative of citations	%	Country
1	1	Library progress	34	4.35	34	4.43	India
2	2	Library philosophy and practice	20	2.56	54	6.90	U.S
3	3	Systematic Biology	15	1.91	69	8.82	U.K
4	4	OCLC Systems and services	13	1.67	82	10.48	U.S
5	5	Library and Information Science research	12	1.54	94	12.02	U.K
6	5	International journal of microstructure	12	1.54	106	13.55	U.K

		and material properties					
7	6	Library connect	10	1.28	116	14.83	U.K
8	6	International journal of library and information Science management	10	1.28	126	16.11	U.K
9	6	Annual of library and information studies	10	1.28	136	17.39	India
10	6	International journal of library Science	9	1.16	145	18.54	Nigeria
11	6	Electronic Library	9	1.16	154	19.69	U.K
12	6	Journal of library and information services	9	1.16	163	20.84	U.S
13	6	DESIDOC journal of library and information technology	9	1.16	172	21.99	India
14	7	IFLA Bulletin	8	1.03	180	23.01	Netherland
15	7	Sciencrometrics	8	1.03	188	24.04	Netherland
16	7	International Journal environment Science	8	1.03	196	25.06	India
17	7	Journal of Economics issues	8	1.03	204	26.08	U.S
18	7	Journal of the society of Archivist	8	1.03	212	27.10	U.K
19	8	Journal of theoretical and applied information technology	7	0.89	219	28.00	Pakistan
20	8	Open educational resources	7	0.89	226	28.90	U.S
21	8	The journal of the Asian finance ,economics and business	7	0.89	233	29.79	South Korea
22	8	Journal of the Australian library and information association	7	0.89	240	30.69	Australia
23	9	Serials review	6	0.77	246	31.45	U.K
24	9	Reference services and systems	6	0.77	252	32.22	U.K
25	9	Information systems and economic intelligence	6	0.77	258	32.99	Netherland
26	9	IFLA Library	6	0.77	264	33.75	Netherland
27	10	journal of library & information services in distance learning	5	0.64	269	34.39	U.S
28	10	Malaysian journal of library and information science	5	0.64	274	35.03	Malaysia

29	10	journal of applied information science and technology	5	0.64	279	35.67	Nigeria
30	10	Indian journal of management	5	0.64	284	36.31	India
31	10	Imperial journal of interdisciplinary research	5	0.64	289	36.95	India
32	10	IFLA journal	5	0.64	294	37.59	U.K
33	11	Journal of the national Academy of science	4	0.51	298	38.10	U.S
34	11	Journal of information and communication technology	4	0.51	302	38.61	Malaysia
35	11	IASLIC Bulletin	4	0.51	306	39.13	India
36	11	bulletin of the medical library association	4	0.51	310	39.64	U.S
37	12	college and research libraries	3	0.38	313	40.02	U.S
38	12	The international information & library review	3	0.38	316	40.40	U.K
39	12	Remote sensing	3	0.38	319	40.79	Switzerland
40	12	public library trends	3	0.38	322	41.17	France
41	12	PENDIPA journal of science education	3	0.38	325	41.56	Indonesia
42	12	library high technology	3	0.38	328	41.94	U.K
43	12	Academic research journals	3	0.38	331	42.32	U.S
44	12	Australian Academic and research libraries	3	0.38	334	42.71	Australia
45	12	Far Eastern economic review	3	0.38	337	43.09	Hong Kong
46	12	Journal of the china society for scientific and technical	3	0.38	340	43.47	China
47	12	Journal of library and information service and systems	3	0.38	343	43.86	U.S
48	12	journal of applied clinical medical physics	3	0.38	346	44.24	U.S
49	12	International journal of information retrieval research	3	0.38	349	44.62	U.S
50	12	Information journal of library science and information management	3	0.38	352	45.01	India
		45 journals cited with 2 times each 45*2=90	90	11.50	442	56.52	
		340 Journals with 1 citation each	340	43.47	782	100	

	(340*1)				
Total		782	100		

It is observed in Table 4 that Ranking of periodicals. A total of 782 Journals were identified from 1409 citations. There were 34(4.35%) are from the journal of “Library Progress” published from “India”. Followed by 20(2.56%) were from journal of “Library philosophy and practice” published from “U.S”, 15(1.91%) were from journal of “Systematic biology” published from “U.K”. and etc.

Table 5 Age wise distribution of journal citations

Sl. no	Years	No. of years	No. of Citations	%
1	1980-1990	10	15	1.91
2	1991-2001	10	30	3.84
3	2002-2012	10	241	30.82
4	2013-2023	10	496	63.43
Total		40	782	100

It is observed in T5 that Age wise distribution of journal citations. A total of 782 Citations were identified from 40 years out of which the highest 496(63.43%) were from the period “2013-2023” followed by 241(30.82%) were from “2002-2012”, 30(3.84%) were from “1991-2001” and 15(1.91%) were published from “1980-1990”.

Fig.4 Age wise distribution of journal citations.

11. Findings and conclusions of study

It is observed in table 1 that a total of 1409 citations were identified from 45 PG dissertations. The highest 15(33.33%) number of dissertations were submitted in 2021.

T1

It is observed in table 2 that A total of 1409 citations were identified out of which the highest 782(55.50%) were from “Journal articles”. **T2**

It is observed in Table 3 that a total of 782 citations there are 305(39.01%) were “Single Author”. **T3**

It is observed in Table 4 that a total of 782 Journals were identified from 1409 citations. The highest 34(4.35%) are from the journal of “Library Progress” published from “India”. **T4**

It is observed in Table 6 that A total of 782 Citations were identified from 40 years out of which the highest 496(63.43%) were from the period “2013-2023”. **T5**

Conclusion:

The bibliometric analysis of post –graduation dissertations in library and information Science at BNU during the year reveals a diverse range of research topics, with a focus on of research topics, with, information retrieval, and knowledge management. The study found an increase in the number of dissertations published during this period, indicating a growing research output.

This comprehensive bibliometric analysis of renewable energy research provides detailed insights into the evolving landscape of this critical field. Bibliometric has emerged as the most active field of library and information science. This bibliometric analysis provides a comprehensive overview of the research trends, patterns, and insights into the productivity, impact, and collaboration of authors, institutions, and countries. This study demonstrates the value of bibliometric analysis in informing strategic decisions, identifying areas for improvement, and guiding future research directions.

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